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DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TOOLS FOR THE FORMATION OF PUPILS' HUMANITARIAN CULTURE TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE MULTIVARIANCE OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE ADDITIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the use of digital educational tools for the formation of students' humanitarian culture taking into account the polyvariance of the English language in the system of additional foreign language education (SFLE). An important direction of digitalisation of foreign language education is the use of neurotechnologies, wireless communication technologies, which ensure the functioning of the whole system of continuous foreign language education. This methodology makes it possible to train future specialists, form their personal qualities and professional competences. The main task of a teacher of foreign languages (FL) in the supplementary foreign language education (SLE) is to improve students' speech skills and abilities purposefully and consciously in the process of performing special tasks in listening, speaking, reading, with the help of digital technologies. In this article, the author of the study emphasises the fact that in the classes of SFLE it is important for the teacher not only to ensure learning of the specific language units, but also to develop communicative skills on the basis of digital educational tools, which later become the basis for the intercultural communication for students. A teacher of FL should try to choose the appropriate digital technology, implement it, realise the proposed methods of language teaching or, based on them, develop his/her own methodology in accordance with the students' experience and abilities in the conditions of digital transformation of foreign language education.

Keywords: a foreign language, digital educational technologies, humanitarian culture, a learner, polyvariant English, digital resources, additional foreign language education

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ЦИФРОВЫЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ИНСТРУМЕНТЫ ДЛЯ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ГУМАНИТАРНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ УЧАЩИХСЯ С УЧЕТОМ ПОЛИВАРИАНТНОСТИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В ДОПОЛНИТЕЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена использованию цифровых образовательных инструментов для формирования гуманитарной культуры обучающихся с учетом поливариантности английского языка в системе дополнительного иноязычного образования. Важным направлением цифровизации иноязычного образования является использование нейротехнологий, беспроводных коммуникационных технологий, которые обеспечивают функционирование всей системы непрерывного иноязычного образования. Данная методология позволяет готовить будущих специалистов, формировать их личностные качества и профессиональные компетенции. Главная задача преподавателя иностранных языков в дополнительном иноязычном образовании (ДИО) – целенаправленно и осознанно совершенствовать у обучающихся речевые навыки и умения в процессе выполнения специальных заданий по аудированию, говорению, чтению, с помощью цифровых технологий. В данной статье автор исследования подчеркивает тот факт, что на занятиях по ИЯ в системе ДИО преподавателю важно не только обеспечивать заучивание конкретных языковых единиц, но и развивать коммуникативные навыки на основе цифровых образовательных инструментов, которые в дальнейшем становятся для школьников основой для межкультурного общения. Преподаватель ИЯ в ДИО должен стараться выбирать соответствующую цифровую технологию, внедрить ее, реализовать предложенные методы обучения ИЯ или, опираясь на них, разработать собственную методику в соответствии с опытом и способностями обучающихся в условиях цифровой трансформации иноязычного образования.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, цифровые образовательные технологии, гуманитарная культура, обучающийся, поливариантность английского языка, цифровые ресурсы, дополнительное иноязычное образование

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Introduction

The topic of the article is devoted to teaching a foreign language (FL) in the context of multicultural diversity, as well as the formation of awareness of pupils' using digital tools, awareness of the humanitarian culture.

Due to the fact that the formation of pupils' humanitarian culture is primarily based on the cultural communication and the ability to support a conversation in a FL with the representatives of different linguistic communities. It is relevant according to many researchers, which are W. Labov, B. Bernstein, B. Kachru and others. It is the consideration of teaching a FL from the point of view of sociolinguistics and the theory of language contacts.

In this area, the problems of English are investigated as a universal tool for the transnational communication. In particular, the role of English in non-post-colonial countries is specified, the criteria for humanitarian culture, the procedures and strategies that ensure mutual understanding are determined.

The following approaches to the English language as global are distinguished:

- English as a foreign language, which is based on the monocentric and bicentric model of the English language, when, for example, the British version of the English language and the culture of Great Britain are taken as a basis. Besides, for example, the American version of the English language and the culture of the United States of America;
- in contrast, one can mention such a theory as English as an international language, which was proposed by Larry Smith and is based on the need to familiarize pupils with various options for English that may be required in real life, in conditions of the real communication. This term "English as an international language" means a set of different variants of the English language and is the language of intercultural, inter-ethnic communication;
- in addition, there is another concept – the international English, which exists along with various variants such as American, British, Singaporean, Chinese, and is defined as a special non-localized dialect or a variant of English. In addition, the international English is very often associated with such a concept as English for the specific purposes, which implies a

special register of the language that allows the exchange of experience in special contexts, for example, science culture and technology.

Theoretical background

Thus, we found ourselves in a new linguistic reality. In particular, we faced the problem of determining the status of new options in relation to the traditional British and American versions of the English language in the context of globalization and the choice of samples for teaching English in schools and universities.

It should also be mentioned that according to Lari Smith, who spoke about the problems of English as an international language, this problem should be considered from three positions.

Firstly it is an understanding of the spoken, written and oral forms of the speech production. Secondly, this is an understanding of the meaning of the speech segment. And thirdly this is an understanding of the meaning of the text.

The English accents: https://www.uv.es/anglotic/accents_of_english/01/. can be used as a resource for practicing the perception of various English language options. Here you can get acquainted with the options such as Cockney, Yorkshire option and others.

On this site there are tablets that present the pronunciation features of various combinations of the letters that are the characteristics of this version of the English language.

As an exercise after listening, you can invite pupils to think about the features of their spoken English and ask what difficulties the interlocutor could have, for example, from another non-English-speaking country.

To work out your pronunciation skills, you can use the Notepad website for speech input – a <https://speechpad.rv/> that allows you to translate what you say into the text. This makes it possible to analyze how accurately you pronounce a particular speech passage and how the system recognizes it. You need to choose English and start saying something.

You can also offer work with the following sites, where you can see different variants of English. For example, the Chinese version of English or you can listen to an English native speaker from Russia, Lebanon, and so on:

– the International Archive of the English Dialects <https://www.dialectsarchive.com/>;

– <https://adelphistudio.com/vo-services/accented-english-voiceartists/portuguese-accent-english-voice-over-services/>.

These materials can be used as an example for listening, as additional material to those audio recordings that offer the standard English textbooks.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the view on teaching a foreign language from the perspective of sociolinguistics and the theory of language contacts and the contact variology seems relevant in connection with the changing status of English in the world, including as an intermediary language. In connection with the fact language it is a social phenomenon and that a variety of social and cultural factors must be taken into account for the acquisition of the intercultural communication competence. It is necessary to create real communication situations that include different variations of the language, problem to select the appropriate code in the interpersonal relationships to form successful language contacts.

Material and methods

Many scientists, educators and psychologist, wrote and are writing about the values of the supplementary education for pupils and its developmental prospects, who are reconsidering the importance of this system of education in their research. They include such famous figures as: V. Apilatov, I.A. Belenko. As a social order of society, which is formed in such laws as: “The Federal Law of Education of the Russian Federation”, “The Concept of additional education for Children” there defines a humanitarian nature of education, where the universal human values, human life and health, free development of personality become a priority. As a consequence, the phenomenon of additional education, which integrates pre-school general and professional educational sphere, is a unique social-pedagogical institution.

The purpose of the article – the consideration of the essence of digital education tools in order to form pupils' humanitarian culture taking into account the multivariance of the English Language the additional foreign language education.

Statement of the task. The article is an attempt to identify the functions and conditions of digital edu-

cational tools in teaching the students' foreign language skills as the essential phenomenon of education. To develop the effective methodology – the lessons of English for teaching the oral speech, identifying the area of difficulties in implementing the requirements for the formation of pupils' humanitarian culture and the improvement of their communication skills.

Methods, techniques and technologies used in the study

During the research we used the following methods: analysis, comparison, systematization, specification and generalization, as well as interviewing, observation and testing.

Study and results

The widespread adoption of digital technologies in the modern world is changing not only the private daily life and work activity, but also provides the new opportunities for teaching a FL. Digital resources enable pupils to receive information, communicate with people from all over the world, communicate on the Internet using various offers – (social networks, etc.) and transmit information (for example, upload videos, create websites).

Taking into account the digital transformation serves the purpose of supplementing the modern provisions of education policy, promoting independence through the changes in the meaningful and formal organization of the learning process and the better development of the personal potential in obtaining education, including the digital learning environment.

The possibilities of individualization when using digital technologies arise from the possibility of flexible and easily accessible use of various materials for pupils of different levels and different training purposes. In addition, the material can be purposefully selected to provide learning opportunities for pupils of different levels of study.

Digital technologies help to motivate pupils to learn a foreign language through the use of digital learning tools; provide the possibility of simultaneous use of individual and group forms of educational activities, operational feedback with the pupils. They allow to contribute to the involvement of each student in different activities both during and after online classes; allow continuous monitoring of the pupils' educational achievements, prompt and objective current and intermediate control of the learning material acquisition through electronic testing [2].

Digital technologies contribute to the organization and management of the process of individual training under the control of the teacher, including through the web interface, ensure the continuity of learning stages. There is a flexible system for setting up educational content for a specific student, the ability to build an individual educational route, a developed system of educational communication through the forums, blogs, magazines, wikis and other means of interaction. At the same time, a large number of pupils can be involved in the training process without limiting territorial distance and time limitation [3, p. 181-182].

All this helps to form pupils' humanitarian culture.

In our study we understand the pupils' humanitarian culture as a type of universal culture, characterising the development of the pupil's personality, the level of his humanitarianism, which reflects the degree of mastering the universal humanistic values by students' a spiritual heritage, which leads the personality to comprehend the spiritual and moral foundations of learning activities and the awareness of his culture as his society.

Training platforms, often also referred to as learning management systems, are web infrastructure specifications. We are talking about the installed software on a web server that supports the provision and the use of educational material, promotes communication between the students and the teacher, and also provides the opportunity for collaboration, and individual development. Depending on the structure of the training platform, you can save and share files, create electronic encyclopedias, post and process tasks, communicate by e-mail or chat, send messages, post work plans and work materials and create the links to other electronic content or insert it [9, p. 50]. An increasingly important area of the development is the adaptive learning systems, as they are focused on the individual level of development and knowledge of individual students [9, p. 76].

When creating a digital learning environment, it is necessary to take into account the possibilities of digital resources, planning classes taking into account the possibilities of individualization and increasing the responsibility of students.

With the appropriate technical equipment, it is possible to almost abandon completely the frontal

training and, within the framework of training under personal responsibility, at least at some stages, provide students with the opportunity to make decisions independently, which topic they want to study in a more detail, or in which place there may still be a need for repetition. Taking into account the different individual pace of training, students themselves decide how often to listen to the digital material (audio podcast) or watch, for example, explanatory videos, presentations, reports or educational videos, and/or whether to take a pause for a while, periodically go back and/or move forward. In any case, they can get support, which can be in the form of (a sheet with a written task) or online (for example, an online test, if necessary with a stop function). Additionally, if necessary, a forum can be created with joint students or a teacher. Thus, each of the pupils can achieve individual results, and the teacher can track, and evaluate the work of each pupil.

The organization of a modern, authentic and motivated process of learning a FL can be facilitated by the following:

- the use, recommendations, the creation of explanatory films;
- making proposals for self study;
- the use of software for a text, the voice and video communication over the Internet (for example, Skype, etc.) to get acquainted with the world;
- replacement of outdated training tools;
- authentic search on the real web pages [7];

On the Internet, teachers can find texts of different language levels on different topics at different stages of study, you can offer the same text of different degrees of complexity (for example, news, etc., outlined in a simple and a more complex language). This makes it easier to prepare for a differentiated lesson in a FL in groups of pupils with different levels of language proficiency [10].

For classroom work, training and test systems operating in a computer classroom with a local network can be used. The functionality of such systems allows you to automate the verification of tests performed, correct the incorrect answers of pupils, accumulate the individual and group statistics on the passage of tests by the pupils during the academic year. The use of these systems unloads the teacher significantly, provides each pupil with an individual operating

the mode, and the teacher is engaged in monitoring the execution of tasks and selecting the new tasks for pupils [1, p. 12].

The individual presentation of educational material can be carried out auditively, visually, etc. Individual classes of a teacher with a pupil can be held, for example, in the video conferencing mode [4, p. 51].

The use of digital technologies contributes to self-learning. Independent work using a computer or the digital technologies, that is with training or monitoring a computer program, can include all the types of speech activities. For example, you can work with selected texts individually, select the written tasks by your interest, and conduct individual listening.

Independent training can be organized, for example, based on the use of an interactive library system. Any remote user with an Internet connection can easily install a software application for working with electronic textbooks from the website of the educational organization on his computer. Developed (advanced) capabilities of the educational material, including various types of self-control and support for any multimedia information, make it possible to create the effective self-teachers [1, p. 12], forming pupils' humanitarian culture.

In foreign language education, an electronic portfolio is often used, which provides an opportunity for the individual assessment of the pupil and is an excellent way to assess his knowledge and skills. The pedagogical technology "Quest" is quite applicable in teaching a FL. According to the form of work, quests are divided into individual and group, relate to the project activities, are carried out in several stages, which are implemented in the form of independent work at home and work in the classroom. When using the explanatory videos, tasks are necessarily offered, including for an advanced level, which require the intensive and individual study of the content. In addition, they provide an opportunity to identify the problems of pupils, which the teacher must then pay attention to the in-person classes. Training with a virtual interlocutor (chatbot) contributes to the individual development of pupils' oral speech.

When working on the vocabulary, for example, an online list of words can be used to compile the individual cards with the words for studying and exchanging in a group of pupils. In this case, various platforms

can be used that provide the ability to draw up pre-agreed cards with the words taking into account the individual experience and the needs, exchange them through the platform, access them during training and the individual repetition. You can use online dictionaries as an individual training application if you register there and compile a list of words, which can then be exported or immediately printed on cards.

A dictionary cloud (a cloud of (keywords)) is a way of presenting a brief overview of the information. Keywords stand out in different ways. Depending on the significance, their font size differs. Word clouds can be created in a variety of applications. With the help of such auxiliary programs, you can upload texts or create the keywords yourself. The program counts the encountered terms by frequency and creates a cloud that consists of text terms. The more the terms are found in the text, the larger they are depicted inside the dictionary cloud, and they can be immediately transferred to the program or processed individually. You can change the type of font, color and formal, as well as focus on the certain words.

Discussion

A special place in teaching a FL is occupied by blogs, which are gaining more and more importance due to their motivational potential and multi-prospective nature, which supports pupils in the learning process. This tool provides the opportunity, for example, to create and publish the individual travel reports, etc. In this case, the corresponding records or posts can be supplemented with the comments and their own impressions. The teacher can leave personal comments for individual work with the pupils and monitor the success of the work. From this point of view working with blogs provides an opportunity to form authentic and motivated writing through literary creativity. Sharing personal experience and expressing their opinion, students discover and comprehend their "I," as well as develop an individual author's style in a FL [8, p. 5, 8].

Currently, mobile users have an access to a huge number of special training applications for learning a FL, which are intuitive. The task of the teacher in this case is to assist pupils in choosing the necessary and appropriate products that can maximize language learning, thereby individualizing the learning process.

For example, the applications designed to work on the expansion of vocabulary, including with the help

of classes in a game form, distinguish an individualized approach to the user's needs, in particular, they include such functions as the ability to create individual word lists, voiced words and the contexts of use, an individual training schedule, various types of training tasks, interactive and game components (for example, user success statistics, the cards for repeating the past material, point reward system) [6, pp. 141-142].

A fairly wide range and a variety of existing mobile training resources allow you to choose applications according to the individual needs, interests and the level of the language training of the pupil. Mobile applications can be used effectively enough for independent work.

In addition, there are auxiliary programs that are designed specifically for teachers to see the learning process of individual pupils.

Mobile devices, in particular, smartphones, in this situation should be considered as an individual means of receiving and storing educational content of various kinds and reverse, also individual communication with the teacher.

Conclusion

Thanks to the use of tablets in the learning process, it is possible to organize an individual educational process and at the same time provide a feedback using the gadget. This also unloads teachers

who, due to the increased number of pupils, are unable to assess constantly the success of training for all pupils in the classroom [9, p. 94].

Thus, digital resources provide an opportunity to individualize the learning process, to offer a variety of differentiated tasks, in the preparation of which the teacher can avoid collective write-off or copying, that all forms the cognitive component of the humanitarian culture. Thanks to different digital resources, the teacher can detect specific problem areas, and take an individual approach to the individual pupils.

The learning process can be tailored individually through the interactive materials, educational videos, and more. The use of educational videos, web quests or an electronic portfolio creates the opportunity, among other things, to implement an individual approach to teaching a FL when using digital technologies. This motivates pupils, promotes self-learning and leads to a stable learning process. In addition, thanks to this, training time can be used more efficiently.

The use of digital technologies in teaching a FL in the future will lead to new knowledge in the certain areas, which will be used to create the adaptive educational materials that promote individual learning and improve it, that will form pupils' humanitarian culture.

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